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Nested Numeric/Geometric/Arithmetic Properties of shCherbak's Prime Quantum 037 as a Base of (Biological) Coding/Computing

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Abstract

Numerous arithmetical regularities of nucleon numbers of canonical amino acids for quite different systematizations of the genetic code, which are dominantly based on decimal number 037, indicate the hidden existence of a more universal ordering principle. Mathematical analysis of number 037 reveals that it is a unique decimal number from which an infinite set of self-similar numbers can be derived with the nested numerical, geometrical, and arithmetical properties, thus enabling the nested coding and computing in the (bio)systems by geometry and resonance. The omnipresent fractal structural and dynamical organization, as well as the intertwining of quantum and classical realm in the physical and biological systems could be just the consequence of such coding and computing.

Key Words: genetic code, nested codes, numeral systems, cyclotomic polynomials and lattice, figured numbers, biocomputing, golden mean

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Introduction

All living organisms are fundamentally based on *information*, which holds a central role in their communication and control, and therefore in their structural and dynamical organization. Such contemporary comprehension of living organisms as information systems is the result of a long-lasting history during which the *biological field theory* has been developed (Gurwitsch, 1912, 1923; Glauber, 1963; Waddington, 1966; Fröhlich, 1968; Presman, 1970; Popp, 1989, 1992). This approach places the *biological coding/computing* at the very heart of the biological organization, as well as its origin and evolution, since the *organic codes (biological codes, biocodes) can be considered as the basic mechanism of macroevolution* (Barbieri, 1998; 2008).

Thus, the crucial challenge biological organisms meet is the generation, transmission, reception, and storage of information with high fidelity due to continuous noise in the system, which according to the information theory requires involving the *error-correcting codes*. The simplest realization of error-correcting codes is achieved by a layered structure referred to as the *nested codes*, a special type of the concatenated error-correcting codes where the result of a previous encoding process is combined with new information and then encoded again, so that the deepest nested information is also the best protected one and does not demand very efficient individual codes, which in terms of biocodes means "...the older and more fundamental it is, the better it is protected" (Battail, 2007). Such biocodes nesting, i.e. their coexistence and overlapping, was first discovered by Trifonov (1980; 1989) for the *coexisting triplet code* (a sequence of instructions for protein synthesis) and *chromatin code* (a sequence of instructions for nucleosome positioning). The logic of nesting or fractality

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reduces the problem to the first generative set/mapping – the *fractal generator*, which means, in terms of biological coding/computing, the reduction to the first biocode/biocomputation - *genetic code* and *translation*, since Woese (1965) shows in his early work that the translation process was highly developed at the bottom of the universal phylogenetic tree, even in comparison to the simpler process of transcription, while replication still did not exist at that level. Since the genetic code, as the first biocode, represents not only the origin of life, but also the *link between physical and biological coding/computing*, the understanding of mathematical logic of the genetic code is of special interest, and was suddenly made possible by shCherbak's revealing arithmetic inside the universal genetic code (Shcherbak's, 1994).

ShCherbak's arithmetic inside the universal genetic code

Almost two decades ago, shCherbak (1994) made astonishing discovery of the arithmetic regularities of nucleons inside the genetic code. The history of this discovery (shCherbak, 2003) began soon after the code decrypting, when it was recognized that the correlation between amino acid mass and codon distribution existed in a sense that the smaller amino acid size requires the greater number of codons for its translating and vice versa (Schutzenberger *et al.*, 1969). This antisymmetrical correlation was confirmed by introducing an integer-valued parameter – a *nucleon number* (a sum of protons and neutrons in atomic nucleus) (Hasegawa and Miyata, 1980), which motivated very extensive shCherbak's researches of arithmetical regularities in the genetic code (Shcherbak, 1994; 2003; 2008). The initial shCherbak's key result is revealing the determination of symmetrical architecture of genetic code by *decimal number 037* through arithmetical regularities of nucleon numbers for the free molecules of canonical amino acids and nucleotide bases, with remark that the number 037 is unique in decimal system in the sense that its *three digit multiples* remain multiples modulo 9 by *cyclic permutations* (Tab. 1) and that similar numbers also exist in some other numeral systems ($[13]_4$, $[25]_7$, $[49]_{13}$) (Shcherbak, 1994). The number 037 was called a *Prime*

Quantum – PQ by shCherbak (Shcherbak, 1994; 2003) or later just a *Prime Number – PN* (shCherbak, 2008).

Table 1. Multiplicative table of number 037.

001	002	003	004	005	006	007	008	009	1 st (a) Row
037	074	111	148	185	222	259	296	333	
010	011	012	013	014	015	016	017	018	2 nd (a) row
370	407	444	481	518	555	592	629	666	
019	020	021	022	023	024	025	026	027	3 rd (a) Row
703	740	777	814	851	888	925	962	999	

ShCherbak pointed out a variety of different nucleon arithmetic regularities, including those for the *free* form amino acids and peptide *bonded* amino acids (the standard block residues and the ionized and protonated side chains); for the *compressed*, *life-size*, and *split* representation of genetic code; for Rumer's and Gamow's division of genetic code, and many other regularities (shCherbak, 2003; 2008).

As an explanation for the found arithmetical regularities based on *PQ 037*, shCherbak (2003) suggested that “the divisibility by *PQ* as a validation criterion, if any, simplifies molecular machinery and facilitates the computational procedure of hypothetical organelles working as biocomputers”, since to very simple divisibility rule of 37 for base 10 by the checking divisibility for the *sum of three digit block of number*, which “...requires only the three digit register”. Generally, this divisibility “...criterion is valid for the $PQ = \langle 1_n 1_{n-1} \dots 1_1 \rangle_q / n$, if the condition $(q-1)/n = \text{Int}$ is applied and the *n*-digit reading frame is used” (shCherbak, 2003).

ShCherbak's results motivated other researchers to further reveal arithmetical regularities and their deeper mathematical and physical principles (Verkhovod 1994; Downes and Richardson, 2002; Rakočević, 1998; 2004; Négadi, 2009; 2011; Mišić, 2004; 2010), but the purpose of such evident correlation between the genetic coding and the quantized nucleon packing of its constituents through the *037 nucleon packing quantum* has remained unclear. So, the question arises - why 037?

Self-similar numbers

A good way of understanding the properties of a number is its generalization. Let us call

Self-similar Number (\mathcal{S}) every integer which has the property of decimal number 037 in an arbitrary numeral system, i.e. the analogue multiplicative table of number 037 (Tab. 1) (Mišić, 2010). This property of \mathcal{S} has been defined as a special case of *cyclic equivariability* or, more precisely, an *equidistant cycling digit property*². It can be proved that the definition of \mathcal{S} is valid both for the condition of *multipliers equidistance* and the condition of *digits equidistance*.

Definition 1A (Mišić, 2010) Self-similar number $\mathcal{S}_p(q)=\mathcal{S}$ of a given numeral system, radix $q \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1\}$, is the smallest nontrivial p -digit number, $p \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1\}$, whose successive cyclic permutations are equal to its own equidistant multiples, except for the permutation which results in \mathcal{S} .

Definition 1B Self-similar number $\mathcal{S}_p(q)=\mathcal{S}$ of a given numeral system, radix $q \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1\}$, is the smallest nontrivial p -digit number, $p \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1\}$, with cyclic digit property whose digits are equidistant.

The trivial forms of numbers with equidistant cycling digit property are represented by the *repdigits*, $\underbrace{aa \dots aa}_p q$,

where $a \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, q-1\}$ is q -nary digit.

Both definitions indicate that general solution, i.e. the solution for each p , exists only for *right-shift* cyclic permutations, while in the case of *left-shift* it does not exist, i.e. the solution exists only in the case of doublets (biplets) when it is equalized with that of the *right-shift*. This general solution for \mathcal{S} is determined by the following equation (Mišić, 2010):

$$\mathcal{S}_p(q) = \overbrace{a_{p-1} a_{p-2} \dots a_0} \begin{cases} a_i = (p-1-i) \frac{q-1}{p}, i=1, \dots, p-1 \\ a_0 = (p-1) \frac{q-1}{p} + 1 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $a_i \in \{0, 1, \dots, q-1\}$ is a q -nary digit on the i th position.

² "If a fraction m/n has a nonterminating decimal expansion, the block of repeating digits is called the *repetend* of m/n . An integer n has the *cycling digits property* if every fraction m/n has a repetend that is a cyclic permutation of the repetend of $1/n$ " (Kalman, 1996).

The solution could be expressed in a simple form (Mišić, 2010; cf. shCherbak, 2003):

$$\mathcal{S}_p(q) = \frac{R_p(q)}{p}, \quad (2)$$

where $R_p(q)$ is p th *repunit* in the numeral system of radix q , given as

$$R_p(q) = \underbrace{11 \dots 11}_p q = q^{p-1} + q^{p-2} + \dots + q + 1. \quad (3)$$

Eq. (1) gives the necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of \mathcal{S} in numeral system of arbitrary radix q ,

$$\frac{q-1}{p} \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (4)$$

which is minimally satisfied for $p = q - 1$, and thus in each numeral system there exists at least one \mathcal{S} .

The graphic representation of Eq. (1) (Fig. 1) shows interdependence between the equidistant multiplying and equidistant digit distribution of numbers with the cycling digit property. In Fig. 1, it can be observed that each \mathcal{S} has the analogue numbers for other radix q and multipletness p , so called \mathcal{S} analogues (\mathcal{S}^A) (Mišić, 2010). Two groups of \mathcal{S}^A can be distinguished - those with the same number of digits (vertically arranged) and those with similar digits [horizontally arranged, Eq. (6)], which is leading to the definition of "vertical" and "horizontal" \mathcal{S} analogues (Fig. 1).

Definition 2 Self-similar numbers $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_p(q)$ for constant p and variable q are the *vertical analogues of class p* or *p -plets*.

The successive vertical \mathcal{S}^A have the radix difference p and the digit difference $0, 1, 2, \dots, p-2, p-1$, respectively.

Definition 3 Self-similar numbers $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_p(q)$ for variable q and p with the constant $(q-1)/p$ are the *horizontal analogues of order $(q-1)/p$* .

The successive horizontal \mathcal{S}^A , for instance of order 3, enable the next transformation:

$$0369D_{16} \xleftarrow{D_{16}=10_{13}} 036A_{13} \xleftarrow{A_{13}=10_{10}} 037_{10} \xleftarrow{7_{10}=10_7} 04_7 \quad (5)$$

This transformation is much more obvious if the extension of digit notation for higher radix digits is based on decimal numbers, i.e. if $A = \overline{10}$, $B = \overline{11}$, $C = \overline{12}$, $D = \overline{13}$..., then

$$036913_{16} \xrightarrow{\overline{13}_{16}=\overline{10}_{13}} 03610_{13} \xrightarrow{\overline{10}_{13}=\overline{10}_{10}} 037_{10} \xrightarrow{\overline{7}_{10}=\overline{10}_7} 04_7 \quad (6)$$

The fact that some \mathcal{S} have vertical and horizontal analogues in the *same* numeral system, enables the defining of the third kind of analogues (Fig. 1).

Definition 4 Self-similar numbers $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_p(q)$ for variable q and p so that $q = p^2 + 1$ are the *diagonal analogues*.

Figure 1. The regular digits distribution of \mathcal{S} in dependence of numeral system radix q and digit multiplicity p . The colored arrows denote three types of \mathcal{S} analogues. Vertical and horizontal analogues are shown for the case of number 037, while the diagonal analogues are unique and independent of the particular case (Mišić, 2010).

The main property of \mathcal{S} results from Eqs. (2) and (3), which shows that \mathcal{S} for (prime) multiplicity p are related to (irreducible) cyclotomic polynomials

$$\Phi_p(q) = \frac{q^p - 1}{q - 1} = q^{p-1} + q^{p-2} + \dots + q + 1 = R_p(q), \quad (7)$$

and thus to the p th roots of unity in complex domain, $\zeta^p = 1$ and $\zeta_i = e^{2\pi i/p}$ (Mišić, 2010). This relationship of self-similar numbers with cyclotomic polynomials, which describe regular polygons, is in the correlation with their definition as the numbers which are equidistantly multiplied by regular cycling of their digits.

Cyclotomic polynomial, Eq. (7), can be regarded as a complementary form of generalized Golden polynomial

$$\phi_p(q) = q^{p-1} - q^{p-2} - \dots - q - 1, \quad (8)$$

whose largest root on the open interval (1, 2) is the generalized Golden Mean (Miles, 1960), wherefrom the relation of \mathcal{S} to generalized Golden Means follows (cf. Tab. 6) (Mišić, 2010).

In the case of the basic form of Golden Mean, $\phi = (\pm 1 \pm \sqrt{5})/2$, and its golden polynomials,

$$\phi_3(q) = q^2 - q - 1, \quad (9)$$

$$\overline{\phi}_3(q) = \phi_3(-q) = q^2 + q - 1, \quad (10)$$

complementary cyclotomic polynomials are obtained,

$$\Phi_3(q) = q^2 + q + 1, \quad (11)$$

$$\overline{\Phi}_3(q) = \Phi_3(-q) = q^2 - q + 1, \quad (12)$$

whose roots are $\zeta_{1,2} = (\pm 1 + i\sqrt{3})/2$ and $\zeta_{4,5} = (\pm 1 - i\sqrt{3})/2$, together with $\zeta_{0,3} = \pm 1$, give the vertices of regular hexagon (this complementarity for more general case is given in Tab. 6). This is in consistence with the fact that triplets \mathcal{S} represent the centered hexagonal numbers (Mišić, 2004; 2010).

Fractal properties of decimal varieties of number 037

In the previous Section it has been shown that \mathcal{S} has analogues in other numeral systems, so it is questionable whether it has its varieties in the same numeral system. The extension of \mathcal{S} for the given numeral system can be done by modifying repunit in Eq. (2). Since \mathcal{S} is fundamentally related to equidistantness (Defs. 1A and 1B), then the equidistant extension of repunit, Eq. (3), with preserving divisibility in Eq. (2), can be done by the two operations – equidistant

insertion $I_n(\cdot)$ and equidistant concatenation $C_n(\cdot)$, that are respectively described by

$$R_p^{I_n}(q) = I_n(R_p(q)) = \underbrace{0 \cdots 0}_{n-1} \underbrace{10 \cdots 0}_{n-1} \cdots \underbrace{10 \cdots 0}_{n-1} \underbrace{010 \cdots 01}_{n-1} q = R_p(q^n), \quad (13)$$

$$R_p^{C_n}(q) = C_n(R_p(q)) = \underbrace{1 \cdots 1}_{p} \underbrace{11 \cdots 11}_{p} \cdots \underbrace{1 \cdots 1}_{p} \underbrace{11 \cdots 11}_{p} q = R_{p \times n}(q). \quad (14)$$

According to Eqs. (2), (13) and (14), it is possible to define two types of \mathcal{S} varieties (\mathcal{S}^v).

Definition 5 The n th vertical variety of \mathcal{S} , denoted as $\mathcal{S}^\downarrow = \mathcal{S}_p^{n\downarrow}(q)$, for the given numeral system q and digit multiplicity p is

$$\mathcal{S}_p^{n\downarrow}(q) = \frac{R_{p, I_n}(q)}{p} = \frac{R_p(q^n)}{p}; (n \in \mathbb{N}). \quad (15)$$

Definition 6 The n th horizontal variety of \mathcal{S} , denoted as $\mathcal{S}^\rightarrow = \mathcal{S}_p^{n\rightarrow}(q)$, for the given numeral system q and digit multiplicity p is

$$\mathcal{S}_p^{n\rightarrow}(q) = \frac{R_{p, C_n}(q)}{p} = \frac{R_{p \times n}(q)}{p}; (n \in \mathbb{N}). \quad (16)$$

From Eqs. (13) and (14) it follows that \mathcal{S}^v can be extended only in the direction of increasing values of q and p ($q \rightarrow q^n$ and $p \rightarrow p \times n$), while \mathcal{S}^A can be extended in both directions ($q - p \leftarrow q \rightarrow q + p$ and $p - 1 \leftarrow p \rightarrow p + 1$), which is the main difference in their notation (Tab. 2).

Table 2. The notations of $\mathcal{S}_p(q)$ modifications.

	Vertical (\downarrow, \downarrow)	Horizontal ($\leftrightarrow, \rightarrow$)	
Analogues \mathcal{S}^A ($\downarrow, \leftrightarrow$)	$\mathcal{S}_p^{m\downarrow}(q) = \mathcal{S}^\downarrow$ $p = \text{const}$	$\mathcal{S}_p^{m\leftrightarrow}(q) = \mathcal{S}^{\leftrightarrow}$ $(q-1)/p \neq \text{const}$	$m \in \mathbb{Z}$ $q \neq \text{const}$
Varieties \mathcal{S}^v (\downarrow, \rightarrow)	$\mathcal{S}_p^{n\downarrow}(q) = \mathcal{S}^\downarrow$ $p \neq \text{const}$	$\mathcal{S}_p^{n\rightarrow}(q) = \mathcal{S}^{\rightarrow}$ $p \neq \text{const}$	$n \in \mathbb{N}$ $q = \text{const}$

q – base radix, p – number of digits,
 m – order of analogue, n – order of variety.

The \mathcal{S}^v are defined so that the first \mathcal{S} variety, for $n=1$, reduces to \mathcal{S} and Eqs. (15) and (16) to Eq. (2). For $n \geq 2$, Eq. (15) reduces to

$$\mathcal{S}_p^{n\downarrow}(q) = \mathcal{S}_p(q^n), \quad (17)$$

which means that the initial extension of p -plet \mathcal{S} to $p \times n$ -plet in same radix q is equivalent to the scaling of p -plet \mathcal{S} in radix q^n (for instance, $\mathcal{S}_3^{2\downarrow}(10) = 003367_{10} = \mathcal{S}_3(10^2) = \overline{003367}_{100}$), and which is actually vertical \mathcal{S}^A for radix q^n and thus this type of varieties is also named vertical (Tab. 3A).

In contrast, the extension of p -plet \mathcal{S} according Eq. (16) results in

$$\mathcal{S}_p^{n\rightarrow}(q) = \mathcal{S}_p(q^n) \times R_n(q) = \mathcal{S}_{p \times n}(q) \times n, \quad (18)$$

so $\mathcal{S}_p^{n\rightarrow}(q)$ has not p -plet \mathcal{S} counterpart for the scaled radix q^n , but leads to $p \times n$ -plet in the same radix q , which is comparable to horizontal \mathcal{S}^A (variable p -plets, $\mathcal{S}^{\leftrightarrow}$) and hence the name horizontal \mathcal{S}^v , $\mathcal{S}^{\rightarrow}$. The relation between vertical and horizontal \mathcal{S}^v for the number 037 is given in Tab. 3A.

Since \mathcal{S}^\downarrow show very interesting property of numerical scaling, we will focus on them, especially on the triplets \mathcal{S} which are the centered hexagonal numbers, in order to examine their potential geometrical and arithmetical scaling. It can be proved that all \mathcal{S}^\downarrow for the triplets ($\mathcal{S}_3^{n\downarrow}(q)$, for $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}$) also represent the centered hexagonal numbers, which are given specifically for the vertical decimal varieties of number 037 (Tab. 3B).

The erasing of digits in \mathcal{S}^v (Tab. 3) which result from inserted and concatenated positions by Eqs. (13) and (14) (normal formatted digits in \mathcal{S}^v and in the indexes) reduces expressions to the original ones (the first row in Tab. 3).

Table 3. Decimal varieties of number 037.

A) Relation between horizontal and vertical decimal varieties of 037	B) Relation between vertical decimal varieties of 037 and centered hexagonal numbers
$111/3 = \mathbf{037} \xrightarrow{\times 1/1} \mathbf{037} = 111/3$	$\mathcal{S}_3(10) = \mathbf{037} = {}^cH_4 = 6 \times T_3 + 1$
$111111/3 = \mathbf{037037} \xrightarrow{\times 1/11} \mathbf{003367} = 010101/3$	$\mathcal{S}_3^{2\downarrow}(10) = \mathbf{003367} = {}^cH_{34} = 6 \times T_{33} + 1$
$111111111/3 = \mathbf{037037037} \xrightarrow{\times 1/111} \mathbf{000333667} = 001001001/3$	$\mathcal{S}_3^{3\downarrow}(10) = \mathbf{000333667} = {}^cH_{334} = 6 \times T_{333} + 1$
...	...

T_n – n th trigonal (triangular) number, cH_n – n th centered hexagonal number.

Each \mathcal{S}^\downarrow reflects the same kind of vertical and horizontal analogy as the original \mathcal{S} (Defs. 2 and 3; Fig. 1), since \mathcal{S}^\downarrow is reduced to \mathcal{S} for powered radix, i.e. q^n . Consequently, the vertical successive analogues of \mathcal{S}^\downarrow have the radix difference p and the digit differences, for instance in the case $n=3$, equal to $0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, \dots, p-1, p-1, p-1$, respectively, while the horizontal successive analogues of \mathcal{S}^\downarrow , for instance of order 3, enable the following analogue transformation to Eq. (6):

$$\begin{aligned} & \overline{00336699}_{12} \overline{13}_{16} \xrightarrow{\overline{13}_{16} = 10_{13}} \overline{00336699}_{10} \overline{13}_{13} \\ & \xrightarrow{\overline{10}_{13} = 10_{10}} \overline{003367}_{10} \xrightarrow{\overline{7}_{10} = 10_7} \overline{0034}_7 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Further scaled or nested properties of \mathcal{S}^\downarrow are manifested in their multiplicative table (Tabs. 4 and 5), because according to Eqs. (17) and (18) all these numbers satisfy

$$\mathcal{S}_p^{n\downarrow}(q) = \mathcal{S}_p(q^n) = \frac{q^{p \times n} - 1}{p(q^n - 1)}, \quad (20)$$

and thus are related to the $p \times n$ th roots of unity, $\zeta^{p \times n} = 1$, and represent the numbers with cyclic digit property. Concretely, for $\mathcal{S}_3^{n\downarrow}(10)$ and $n=1, 2, 3$, it is getting respectively

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{037} \times \mathbf{027} = \mathbf{999}, \\ & \mathbf{003367} \times \mathbf{000297} = \mathbf{999999}, \\ & \mathbf{000333667} \times \mathbf{000002997} = \mathbf{999999999}, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

and so on *ad infinitum*, where $\mathbf{027} = \mathbf{3} \times \mathbf{9}$, $\mathbf{000297} = \mathbf{3} \times \mathbf{99}$, $\mathbf{000002997} = \mathbf{3} \times \mathbf{999}$, ... [the divisors in Eq. (20)].

The partial multiplicative table of number $\mathbf{003367}$, given in Tab. 4, represents its most regular multiplier distribution whose successive differences for (a)-rows are 1, and for (b)-rows are 10. The second and third (a)-rows in Tab. 4, for numbers made up of different digits, are obtained by cyclic

permutation of *two* digit blocks of the first (a)-row according to the same rule in Tab. 1, and generally, (a)-rows (bold numbers) represent original multiplicative table of $\mathbf{037}$ scaled by 2 [$n=2$ in Eqs. (13) and (15)]. The (b)-rows, obtained by right-shift cyclic permutation of the leftmost digit of congruent numbers in (a)-rows, together with the first congruence class form the set of most regular (almost perfectly equidistant) multipliers whose differences are 10 (grey shaded fields in Tab.4).

Similarly, the partial multiplicative table of number $\mathbf{000333667}$, given in Tab. 5, represents its most regular multiplier distribution whose successive differences for (a)-rows are 1, for (b)-rows are 10, and for (c)-rows are 100. The second and third (a)-rows in Tab. 5, for the numbers made up of different digits, are obtained by cyclic permutation of *three* digit blocks of the first (a)-row according to the same rule in Tab. 1, and generally (a)-rows (bold numbers) represent the original multiplicative table of $\mathbf{037}$ scaled by 3 [$n=3$ in Eqs. (13) and (15)]. Erasing every third digit in the numbers of (b)-rows in Tab. 5, reduces them to (b)-rows in Tab. 4 (for instance, a multiple $\mathbf{00336670} \rightarrow \mathbf{033670}$ and a multiplier $\mathbf{0000010} \rightarrow \mathbf{000010}$), while erasing the grey digits in the numbers of any row results in Tab. 1, indicating that in Tab. 5 are nested both Tab. 1 and Tab. 4.

Since $\mathcal{S}_3(q)$ and $\mathcal{S}_3^{n\downarrow}(q)$ are both centered hexagonal numbers (Tab. 3), it is interesting to examine whether their multiples also have some geometrical meaning. For the first three multiples of $\mathcal{S}_3(10)$ and $\mathcal{S}_3^{n\downarrow}(10)$ it is shown that $\mathcal{S}_3(10)$ are related to polygonal numbers (Fig. 2A-C) and according to *nested* principle it is also valid for $\mathcal{S}_3^{n\downarrow}(10)$ (Fig. 3), which generally

indicates the *nested numerical, arithmetical, and geometrical properties of $\mathcal{S}_3(q)$ and their $\mathcal{S}_3^{n\downarrow}(q)$* , which is consequently valid for 037 and its varieties.

Table 4. Partial multiplicative table of number 003367.

000001 003367	000002 006734	000003 010101	000004 013468	000005 016835	000006 020202	000007 023569	000008 026936	000009 030303	1 st (a) row
000010 033670	000020 067340	000030 101010	000040 134680	000050 168350	000060 202020	000070 235690	000080 269360	000090 303030	1 st (b) row
000100 336700	000101 340067	000102 343434	000103 346801	000104 350168	000105 353535	000106 356902	000107 360269	000108 363636	2 nd (a) row
000109 367003	000119 400673	000129 434343	000139 468013	000149 501683	000159 535353	000169 569023	000179 602693	000189 636363	2 nd (b) row
000199 670033	000200 673400	000201 676767	000202 680134	000203 683501	000204 686868	000205 690235	000206 693602	000207 696969	3 rd (a) row
000208 700336	000218 734006	000228 767676	000238 801346	000248 835016	000258 868686	000268 902356	000278 936026	000288 969696	3 rd (b) row

Small numbers are the multipliers of 003367, while big numbers are the proper multiples of 003367. Bold numbers result from the original multiplicative table of 037 (Tab. 1) scaled by 2 [$n=2$ in Eqs. (13) and (15)]. Grey digits are the result of the inserted positions introduced by Eq. 13, and their erasing reduces all numbers to the original Tab. 1 (for bold and normal formatted numbers, respectively). Normal numbers are obtained by the right-shifting of leftmost digit and, together with the first congruence class, they consist of a set of most regular (almost perfectly equidistant) multipliers whose successive differences are 10 (grey shaded fields).

Table 5. Partial multiplicative table of number 000333667.

00000001 000333667	00000002 000667334	00000003 001001001	00000004 001334668	00000005 001668335	00000006 002002002	00000007 002335669	00000008 002669336	00000009 003003003	1 st (a) row
00000010 003336670	00000020 006673340	00000030 010010010	00000040 013346680	00000050 016683350	00000060 020020020	00000070 023356690	00000080 026693360	00000090 030030030	1 st (b) row
00000100 033366700	00000200 066733400	00000300 100100100	00000400 133466800	00000500 166833500	00000600 200200200	00000700 233566900	00000800 266933600	00000900 300300300	1 st (c) row
000001000 333667000	000001001 33400667	000001002 334334334	000001003 334668001	000001004 335001668	000001005 335335335	000001006 335669002	000001007 336002669	000001008 336336336	2 nd (a) row
000001009 336670003	000001019 34006673	000001029 343343343	000001039 346680013	000001049 350016683	000001059 353353353	000001069 356690023	000001079 360026693	000001089 363363363	2 nd (b) row
000001099 366700033	000001199 400066733	000001299 433433433	000001399 466800133	000001499 500166833	000001599 533533533	000001699 566900233	000001799 600266933	000001899 633633633	2 nd (c) row
000001999 667000333	000002000 667334000	000002001 667667667	000002002 668001334	000002003 668335001	000002004 668668668	000002005 669002335	000002006 669336002	000002007 669669669	3 rd (a) row
000002008 670003336	000001018 673340006	000001028 676676676	000001038 680013346	000002048 683350016	000002058 686686686	000002068 690023356	000002078 693360026	000002088 696696696	3 rd (b) row
000002098 700033366	000002198 733400066	000002298 766766766	000002398 800133466	000002498 833500166	000002598 866866866	000002698 900233566	000002798 933600266	000002898 966966966	3 rd (c) row

The explanation of Tab. 5 is the same as in Tab. 4, except the fact that the multiplicand is 000333667 and the scaling is done by 3 [$n=3$ in Eqs. (13) and (15)], as well that the most equidistant multipliers successively differ by 100 (grey shaded fields).

Figure 2. Polygonal numbers related to the first three multiples of number 037. A) The *first* multiple of 037 exactly corresponds to the 4th centered hexagonal number, $C_4 = 37$; B) The *second* multiple of 037, with a unit difference, corresponds to the 4th star number, $S_4 = 73$; C) The *third* multiple of 037 exactly corresponds to the 2nd composite triangular number, $T_2 \times C_4 = 111$; D) The *third* multiple of 037, with a unit difference, corresponds to the sum of the 4th centered hexagonal and star number, $S_4 + C_4 = 110$.

Figure 3. Nested polygonal numbers related to the first three multiples of number 037 decimal vertical varieties. The first multiples of 037 varieties exactly successively correspond to the ...3334th centered hexagonal numbers, while the second multiples are bigger for 1 than successive ...3334th star numbers. The third multiples of 037 varieties again exactly correspond to the 2nd composite triangular numbers.

Nested properties of decimal varieties of 037 can be also deduced from the fact that 037 almost perfectly divides all its varieties, for instance: 3367=37x91, 333667=37x9018+1, 33336667=37x900991, 3333366667=37x90090991, 333333666667=37x9009018018+1, and so on (cf. Tab. 6B).

The indicated arithmetical regularities of \mathcal{S}^\downarrow (Tabs. 4 and 5) are actually the consequence of a deeper regularity in the numeral system. Namely, it follows from Eqs. (2) and (4) that the biggest \mathcal{S} for the given numeral system is for $p=q-1$, when a number is obtained in the form (the second row in Fig. 1):

$$\mathcal{S}_{q-1}(q) = 0123 \dots (q-3)(q-1)_q. \quad (22)$$

The importance of $\mathcal{S}_{q-1}(q)$ is in the fact that it represents the period of q -nary numeration of natural numbers, so called *fundamental period* of q -nary numeral system (Fig. 4) (Mišić, 2004). Fundamental period $\mathcal{S}_{q-1}(q)$ and its length $q-1$ are related to the *basic arithmetical periodicity (modularity)* in q -nary system, and thus to the divisibility rule which follows from modular arithmetic.

Figure 4. Decimal numeration of natural numbers results in the periodic number with period 012345679, while its triple value results in the periodic number with period 037 (Mišić, 2004).

The product of $\mathcal{S}_{q-1}(q)$ with factors of $q-1$, for example with $n=(q-1)/p$ according to Eq. (4), gives n -tuple concatenated $\mathcal{S}_p(q)$, which follows from Eq. (18):

$$\mathcal{S}_p^{(q-1)/p \rightarrow}(q) = \mathcal{S}_{q-1}(q) \times \frac{q-1}{p}. \quad (23)$$

Consequently, all $\mathcal{S}_p(q)$ for p prime and $p|q-1$ represent the *elementary periods* of q -nary numeral system where p is their *period length*.

Further characteristic of the fundamental period $\mathcal{S}_{q-1}(q)$ is in its resulting from the product of $\mathcal{S}_p(q)$ and its vertical variety, so that for $n=(q-1)/p$ and from Eqs. (17), (18), and (23) it follows

$$\mathcal{S}_{q-1}(q) = \mathcal{S}_p(q) \times \mathcal{S}_p^{(q-1)/p \downarrow}(q) = \mathcal{S}_p(q) \times \mathcal{S}_p^{(q-1)/p}(q). \quad (24)$$

For diagonal \mathcal{S}^A (Def. 4), when $q-1=p^2$, Eqs. (23) and (24) are reduced to

$$\mathcal{S}_p^{p \rightarrow}(q) = \mathcal{S}_{p^2}(q) \times p, \quad (25)$$

$$\mathcal{S}_{p^2}(q) = \mathcal{S}_p(q) \times \mathcal{S}_p^{p \downarrow}(q) = \mathcal{S}_p(q) \times \mathcal{S}_p(q^p), \quad (26)$$

which in the decimal system makes the following curious numbers and relations,

$$\mathcal{S}_9(10) = 012345679 = 037 \times 000333667, \quad (27)$$

$$\mathcal{S}_3^{3 \rightarrow}(10) = 037037037 = 3 \times 037 \times 000333667. \quad (28)$$

From Fig. 3 and Eq. (27), it also follows that the fundamental period of the decimal system is the product of two polygonal numbers,

$$\mathcal{S}_9(10) = {}^c H_4 \times {}^c H_{334}, \quad (29)$$

and thus it can be considered as a *composite polygonal number* (Fig. 5).

Definition 7 Composite polygonal number is a positive integer that can be entirely factorized into two or more other polygonal numbers.

Figure 5. Noncommutative multiplication of the composite polygonal numbers, shown in number 259, which is the product of two centered hexagonal numbers and also triplet δ , gives two different geometric forms [cf. Eqs. (34), (35), and (37)].

A particular property of composite polygonal numbers is that they have multivariate geometrical form, as in the case of composite number 259, which is 7th multiple of 037 (Fig. 5).

The last particular property of δ to be mentioned in this paper is their relation to the generalized Golden Mean, Eqs. (8), also valid for δ^\downarrow according to Eq. (17), thus transforming Eqs. (8)-(12) as it is shown in Tab. 6. These two types of complementary polynomials that differ only in the signs, give two geometrically complementary solutions. The first solution relates to the Golden Mean and the corresponding numbers 89, 109 with their scaled values, but also to the Fibonacci numbers (Tab. 6A). The second solution relates to the n th roots of unity and *cyclotomic values* 111, 91 with their scaled values, but also to 037 and its decimal varieties (Tab. 6B), and thus to the centered polygonal numbers (Fig. 3).

Table 6. Comparison between Golden Mean polynomials and cyclotomic polynomials for $q=10$.					
A) Golden Mean polynomials and Fibonacci numbers			B) Cyclotomic polynomials and Self-similarity numbers		
n	$\Phi_{3n}(q) = q^{2n} + q^n - 1$	$1/(q^{2n} + q^n - 1)$	n	$\Phi_{3n}(q) = q^{2n} + q^n + 1$	$(q^{2n} + q^n + 1)/3$
1	109	0,00917431...1284403669724770642018348623853211	1	111	3 x 37
2	010099	0,000009901970...31379344489552113080503020101	2	010101	3 x 3367
3	001000999	0,000000099900197700...21013008005003002001001	3	001001001	3 x 333667
...
n	$\bar{\Phi}_{3n}(q) = q^{2n} - q^n - 1$	$1/(q^{2n} - q^n - 1)$	n	$\bar{\Phi}_{3n}(q) = q^{2n} - q^n + 1$	$(q^{2n} + q^{2n} + 1)/(q^{2n} + q^n + 1)$
1	89	0,0112359550561797752808987640449438202247191	1	91	3367/37
2	9899	0,00010102030508132134559046368320032326497...	2	9901	33336667/3367
3	998999	0,00000100100200300500801302103405508914423...	3	999001	333333666667/333667
...

The regularities in Tab. 6 are valid for any q which satisfies $3|q-1$, i.e. for triplets δ , but only the decimal 037 satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_3^{-1\uparrow}(10) &= \delta_3(7) = \delta_2^{1\leftrightarrow}(5) \text{ and} \\ \delta_3^{-1\leftrightarrow}(10) &= \delta_2(7) = \delta_2^{1\uparrow}(5), \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_3^{1\uparrow}(10) &= \delta_3(13) = \delta_4^{-1\leftrightarrow}(17) \text{ and} \\ \delta_3^{1\leftrightarrow}(10) &= \delta_4(13) = \delta_4^{-1\uparrow}(17). \end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

which means that 037 analogue precursors are the analogue successors of the previous diagonal analogue 035, Eq. (30), and *vice versa* for next diagonal analogue 048D₁₇, Eq. (31) (Fig. 1). Thus, Eqs. (30) and (31) enable general concatenation of diagonal analogues, which are also the only $\delta_p(q)$ with a

fundamental period of q -nary system in the form of the product of $\delta_p(q)$ and its scaled value in the powered radix, Eq. (26). The uniqueness of 037 and thus the decimal system follows from Eq. (29) which has the general form

$$\delta_9^{n\downarrow}(10) = \delta_9(10^n) = {}^c H_{\frac{\dots 334}{n-1}} \times {}^c H_{\frac{\dots 33334}{3n-1}}, \text{ for } \forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \tag{32}$$

and shows that only 10ⁿ-nary systems are completely determined by the centered hexagonal numbers, and thus correlated with the *hexagonal lattice* or *equilateral triangular lattice*. This lattice belongs to the Bravais lattice, an infinite regular array of points in which each lattice point has exactly the same environment in \mathbb{R}^2 (and in \mathbb{R}^3).

The condition for this regular point arrangement is $2\cos(2\pi/N) \in \mathbb{Z}$, which implies that $N=1,2,3,4,6$, for which N is said to be *crystallographic* number and lattice *N-folded Bravais lattice*. Using the cyclotomic ring of order N in the plane, i.e. by the \mathbb{Z} -module, it can be obtained:

$$\mathbb{Z}[\zeta] = \mathbb{Z}[2\cos\frac{2\pi}{N}] + \mathbb{Z}[2\cos\frac{2\pi}{N}]\zeta \quad (33)$$

where $\zeta^N = 1$ and thus $\zeta = e^{2\pi i/N}$.

Eq. (37) results in $\mathbb{Z}[\zeta] = \mathbb{Z}$ for $N=1,2$ giving the whole numbers, $\mathbb{Z}[\zeta] = \mathbb{Z} + \mathbb{Z}i$ for $N=4$ is a square lattice, and $\mathbb{Z}[\zeta] = \mathbb{Z} + \mathbb{Z}e^{i\pi/3}$ for $N=3,6$ is a hexagonal (triangular) lattice. Comparing this with \mathcal{S} reveals that the triplets, $\mathcal{S}_3^{n\downarrow}(q)$, which are the centered hexagonal numbers (Figs. 2 and 3), are also the reduced cyclotomic values for $p=N=3$, Eqs. (2), (3) and (7), and thus really correlated with hexagonal lattice, Eqs. (33). Similarly, it can be proved that the doublets, $\mathcal{S}_2^{n\downarrow}(q)$, are correlated with *square lattice* and with *centered square numbers*, which will be better explained in the next paper.

All the analyses carried out in this Section indicate that, *from the aspect of self-similarity, the number 037 and decimal system are unique integer and numeral systems in the whole realm of numbers and systems, and thus the number 037 has a central place in the whole set of \mathcal{S}^A* (Fig. 1).

Discussion

The most general correspondence between the 037 based coding/computing and the genetic code and its evolution in Woese's sense (Woese, 2002; Vetsigian *et al.* 2006) can be derived from the existence of *horizontal* and *vertical* 037 analogues and its *central* place among them. According to Woese's dynamical theory of genetic code evolution, such process represents the first stage in cellular evolution at the root of the universal phylogenetic tree and it is the result of *communal* evolution of the early life by the *horizontal* gene transfer, so that the universal genetic code is actually a generic consequence of such process and the precondition for the later *individual*

evolution by the *vertical* gene transfer. Similarly, the horizontal 037 analogues are geometrically very *distinctive*, while the vertical are *self-similar*. This mathematical logic is also comparable to Barbieri's mechanism of macroevolution (Barbieri, 1998; 2008) based on two distinct processes, *coding* and *copying*, the first of which creates *absolute* novelties and involves a *collective* set of rules (for instance, *translation*), while the second creates *relative* novelties and operates on *individual* molecules (*transcription*). Because of the need for simultaneous action of both mechanisms, the existence of a universal mechanism which can act in both directions is demanded, and that is the characteristic of 037 based coding/computing by its diagonal analogues.

The reflection of 037 based nested coding/computing must be embodied in other biocodes, like the genomic code. It means that the genomic code must be generally established on the sequence length of 1000 nucleotide as the basic computing frame of number 037 (Mišić, 2010), consistent with the detrended fluctuation analysis that "...clearly supports the difference between coding and noncoding sequences, showing that the coding sequences are less correlated than noncoding sequences for the length scales less than 1000, which is close to characteristic patch size in the coding regions" (Havlin *et al.*, 1995). Moreover, the frequencies of the 64 codons in the whole human genome scale are a self-similar fractal expansion of the universal genetic code and strongly linked to the Golden Mean, indicating that the universal genetic code table predetermines global codon proportions and populations, thus governing both micro and macro behavior of the genome (Perez, 2010), which is also the reflection of 037 based nested coding/computing, since we have shown the complementarity of the number 037 with the Golden Mean (Tab. 6). Rakočević (1998) pointed out that the universal genetic code table is in itself determined by Golden Mean.

The next correspondence with 037 based nested coding/computing will be examined on the nucleic level, since shCherbak (1994) revealed the following

nucleon balances for the canonical DNA base pairs (T=A and C≡G):

$$NN(T,A) = 125 + 134 = 259 = 7 \times 037, \quad (34)$$

$$NN(C,G) = 110 + 150 = 260 = 7 \times 037 + 1, \quad (35)$$

as well as for RNA base U,

$$NN(U) = 111 = 3 \times 037. \quad (36)$$

Besides the exact 037-divisibility of nucleon number for base U, it is also fulfilled for base C with a unit difference, $NN(C) = 110 = 3 \times 037 - 1 = {}^cH_4 + S_4$, which may be geometrically interpreted as in Fig. 2D. For the bases which do not individually correspond to nucleon number 037-divisibility, i.e. bases T, A, and G, their nucleon number differences satisfy the *squares of the first three Pythagorean numbers* ($125 + 3^2 \rightarrow 134 + 4^2 \rightarrow 150$, so $125 + 5^2 \rightarrow 150$, where $125 = 5^3$ is 5th cubic number), the same pattern which appears in Eq. (42). Although the nucleon sums of canonical DNA base pairs and RNA base U are the multiples of 037, they can be also expressed in the form of the *composite polygonal numbers* (Fig. 5 and 2C) and *arithmic*,

$$259 = 7 \times 037 = {}^cH_2 \times {}^cH_4 = \mathcal{S}_3(4) \times \mathcal{S}_3(10) = \mathcal{S}_3^{-2\uparrow}(10) \times \mathcal{S}_3(10) \quad (37)$$

and

$$111 = 3 \times 037 = T_2 \times {}^cH_4 = \mathcal{S}_2(5) \times \mathcal{S}_3(10). \quad (38)$$

In spite of the “imperfect” divisibility of nucleon number for C≡G pair, it can be a perfect computational feature due to the modular arithmetic, since

$$NN(T,A) \equiv 0 \pmod{037}, \quad (39)$$

$$NN(C,G) \equiv 1 \pmod{037}, \quad (40)$$

which enables translating the nucleotide sequence into the nucleon binary string, so that the pair C≡G would have the meaning of the unit element and counting, while T=A would have the meaning of the neutral element for additive operation. For the triplet, the similar modular unit mass has the combination of U, C, and G bases

$$NN(U,C,G) = 111 + 110 + 150 = 371 = 10 \times 037 + 1 = T_4 \times {}^cH_4 + 1, \quad (41)$$

which is the universal periodical pattern $(GCU)_n$ in mRNA and appears to be a fossil of a very ancient organization of codons (Trifonov and Bettecken, 1997), and the reason for that can be the fact that the repetitive sequence of this triplet also enables counting.

The last correspondence is on the level of shCherbak's arithmetic inside the genetic code. Starting from the first shCherbak's result of the arithmetical regularities of the genetic code compressed representation for division according the amino acids degeneracy (Shcherbak, 1994) [also Fig. 9 in (shCherbak, 2008)], the relation of nucleon numbers for *blocks+chains=whole molecules* can be expressed in the form of figurate numbers and/or \mathcal{S} arithmetic for the four-codon amino acids as

$$4^2 \times 037 + 3^2 \times 037 = 5^2 \times 037 = {}^cQ_4 \times {}^cH_4 = ({}^cQ_2)^2 \times {}^cH_4 = \mathcal{S}_2^{2\downarrow}(7) \times \mathcal{S}_3(10) = (\mathcal{S}_2^{2\downarrow}(3))^2 \times \mathcal{S}_3(10), \quad (42)$$

where cQ_n is the n th centered quadrigonal (square) number, which for $n=4$ also satisfies the squares of the first three Pythagorean numbers, while for the nonfour-codon amino acids are presented as

$$30 \times 037 + 30 \times 037 = 60 \times 037, \quad (43)$$

where

$$30 \times 037 = (1 + 10 + 19) \times 037 = 037 + 370 + 703 = {}^4Py_4 \times ({}^cQ_5 - 4), \quad (44)$$

and where 4Py_n is the n th square pyramid [037 is also the number of points in a square lattice covered by a disc centered at (0,0) in the form of an octagon (Sloane and Teo, 1984)].

According to the Gamow's division of genetic code [Fig. 7 in: (shCherbak, 2008)], the sum of the side chains for the one half of the set is

$$703 = 19 \times 037 = {}^cH_3 \times {}^cH_4 = \mathcal{S}_3(7) \times \mathcal{S}_3(10) = \mathcal{S}_3^{-1\uparrow}(10) \times \mathcal{S}_3(10), \quad (45)$$

while for the whole molecules of the one set the following equation applies,

$$1665 = 45 \times \mathbf{037} = T_9 \times {}^c H_4. \quad (46)$$

ShCherbak showed that the nucleon number of amino acids side-chains for life-size genetic code is also divisible by 037, which he described as “the scale symmetry of the compressed and life-size code representation” [Eq. (13) of Tab. 2 in: (shCherbak, 2003)]. This result can be also interpreted as the sum of 037 and its first variety,

$$3404 = 92 \times \mathbf{037} = \mathbf{003367} + \mathbf{037} = {}^c H_{34} + {}^c H_4 = \mathcal{S}_3^{2\downarrow}(10) + \mathcal{S}_3(10). \quad (47)$$

This sum was originally found by Négadi, as well as some other refined relations between 37, 3367 and 333667 (Négadi, 2011).

For the life-size representation of genetic code, we have also revealed that the nucleon number of codons which code four-codon amino acids,

$$11988 = 2^2 \times 3^4 \times \mathbf{037} = Q_2 \times Q_9 \times {}^c H_4, \quad (48)$$

is exactly nine times bigger than the nucleon number of four-codon amino acids,

$$1332 = 36 \times \mathbf{037} = 2^2 \times 3^2 \times \mathbf{037} = Q_2 \times Q_3 \times {}^c H_4, \quad (49)$$

which we interpreted as the nested arrangement of the genetic code *itself*, and thus it is realized using the simplest construction of complex errorless codes [the explanation and Fig. 3 in: (Mišić, 2010)].

Rakočević (2004) showed that total molecule mass of canonical amino acids, $2738 = 2 \times \mathbf{037}^2$, as well as their two subsets, 2×703 and 2×666 , are all multiples of 037, but also

$$2738 = 2 \times \mathbf{037}^2 = 2 \times ({}^c H_4)^2 = 2 \times (\mathcal{S}_3(10))^2, \quad (50)$$

while 703 is represented by Eq. (45) and

$$666 = 18 \times \mathbf{037} = ({}^c H_3 - 1) \times {}^c H_4 = (\mathcal{S}_3(7) - 1) \times \mathcal{S}_3(10), \quad (51)$$

where the first factor may be geometrically interpreted as a *hexagonal ring*, as well as in the whole second subset,

$$1332 = 2 \times 666 = 36 \times \mathbf{037} = ({}^c H_4 - 1) \times {}^c H_4 = (\mathcal{S}_3(10) - 1) \times \mathcal{S}_3(10). \quad (52)$$

Besides some minor additional correspondences with figurate number and/or \mathcal{S} arithmetic, there is one that deserves special attention. Namely, all shCherbak's arithmetic inside the genetic code is based on the *rule of formal borrowing* of one nucleon from the side chain to the standard box of amino acid *Proline* (Shcherbak, 1994), which means that *Proline* is the only canonical amino acid with 73 nucleons in the standard box, and thus only equivalent to 4th star number (Fig. 2B),

$$NN(Pro) = 73 = S_4 = 2 \times \mathcal{S}_3(10) - 1. \quad (53)$$

The explanation of the numerous consistent arithmetical regularities of nucleon numbers of canonical amino acids for the quite different systematizations of the genetic code, which are dominantly based on decimal number 037, can be understood only through the existence of a more universal ordering principle. From the presented mathematical properties of number 037, it follows that a more universal order is hidden within the symmetry, particularly in *crystallographic symmetry (hexagonal lattice) related to cyclotomic rings* (Eq. 33), but also in *self-similar symmetry*, and thus inherently linked with space measurement and geometry, Fig. 4, as well as Figs. 2, 3, and 5. This is consistent with the fact that some problems of coding can be reduced to geometrical problems of sphere packing (Slaone, 1984), while some measurement problems can be reduced to the Golden Mean (Stakhov, 1989).

The suggested biological coding/computing based on 037 numerical/geometrical/arithmetical nesting shares some properties with “quantum computing”, pointed out by Penrose and Hameroff (Penrose, 1991; 1994; Hameroff and Penrose, 2003), including the following: 1) the existence of coherent superposition (comparable with the fact that \mathcal{S} inherently contain numbers with self-similar properties); 2) the discrete and cascade property of process (the transformation between \mathcal{S} are also discrete and cascade); 3) the self-collapsing and objective reduction (the \mathcal{S} set is self-reductive and as a self-referential mathematical system it is also objective); 4) the determination by quantum gravity coupled with space-time geometry (the \mathcal{S} are derived from 037 as a nucleon

packing quantum which describes a collective *mass* of particles and they are also in correlation with the regular geometrical arrangement and space measurement); 5) the involving of periodic, crystal-like lattice dipole structure with long range order (the doublet and triplet δ represent the packing quanta for square and hexagonal lattice). Penrose and Hameroff (2003) proposed cytoskeletal microtubules as a biological structure particularly suitable for quantum computation and for whose coherence sustaining, among others, an important role belongs to the coherently ordered water through the dynamical coupling to the protein surface. It is important that microtubules are the cylinders whose walls are *hexagonal lattices* of subunit proteins known as tubulin, while the ordered water next to hydrophilic surfaces such as the tubulin, according to research by Pollack and his collaborators, behaves like a liquid crystalline (Zeng *et al.*, 2006) with the ice-like structure in the form of *hexagonal layers* whose oxygens are not linked by proton bonds like in the ice, but the layers are stacked by interaction of opposite charges (Pollack, 2012). Since mathematical properties of number 037 are also fundamentally related to hexagonal lattice, then biological coding/computing might be actually fundamentally based on hexagonal symmetry and packing. Therefore, water might be the perfect biological coding/computing medium, as the DNA sequence reconstitution from the treated water indicated (Montagnier *et al.*, 2010), and could have had a crucial primordial role (Pollack *et al.*, 2009) both in the selection of life building block, such as canonical nucleic and amino acids, and in principally predetermined evolution of genetic code with small degree of freedom.

Generally, the presented mathematical properties of number 037 and its realization in the genetic code and to a lesser presented extent in genomic code, indicate that the biological coding/computing is essentially the process both geometrical in nature and determined by the self-similar symmetry, giving the base for the *biological large-scale coherence systems* and *biological quantum-classical intertwining*.

Conclusions

ShCherbak's arithmetic inside the genetic code has a firm mathematical foundation in the sense that it is related to the number 037 - a unique decimal number from which an infinite set of self-similar numbers can be derived, with the nested numerical, geometrical, and arithmetical properties. Their correlation with self-similar symmetry, but also with the cyclotomic polynomials and thus the crystallographic lattices, can explain the numerous consistent arithmetical regularities of nucleon numbers of canonical amino acids for quite different systematizations of the genetic code. Biological coding/computing based on the self-similar numbers enables the realization of the nested organic codes, not only as the simplest error-correcting codes, but also as the biological systems with the holistic fractal structural and dynamical organization and thus the large-scale coherence systems, which is one of the main properties of biological organisms. Since such coding/computing is based both on the geometry and optimal space quantization, and on resonance and long-range interactions, the biological organisms reflect the principles of coding/computing in the physical world and deeply interact with it, which also justifies the fact that they are understood as information determined systems. The suggested coding/computing is also correlated with liquid crystalline water, emphasizing its crucial role in life origin and evolution. Mathematical possibility of the infinite nested coding/computing with self-similar numbers enables a limitless physical domain transition, which can potentially explain biological quantum-classical intertwining and general quantum-classical duality.

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Dedication

This article I dedicate to my scientific "teacher", Professor Miloje M. Rakočević, who bridged my scholarly knowledge to the original scientific work.

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